

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN : 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**

SJIF Impact Factor: 7.187

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF CONTROL RELEASE
TABLET OF REPAGLINIDE****Vishal M. Kanoji^{1*}, Dr. Kamble H.V², Dr. Vivek M. Satpute³, Mr. Sugriv R. Ghodake⁴**^{1*}Research student, Loknete Shri Dadapatil Pharate College of Pharmacy Mandavgan Pharata, Ta - Shirur Dist-Pune 412211²Principal, Loknete Shri Dadapatil Pharate College of Pharmacy Mandavgan Pharata, Ta - Shirur Dist-Pune 412211³Research Guide, Loknete Shri Dadapatil Pharate College of Pharmacy Mandavgan Pharata, Ta - Shirur Dist-Pune 412211⁴Research Co-Guide, Loknete Shri Dadapatil Pharate College of Pharmacy Mandavgan Pharata, Ta - Shirur Dist-Pune 412211**Abstract:**

This study focuses on the formulation and evaluation of sustained-release matrix tablets of Repaglinide, a drug widely used for the management of type 2 diabetes. Pre-formulation studies confirmed the physico-chemical properties of Repaglinide, including its melting point, solubility profile, and characteristic functional groups, ensuring the drug's compatibility for sustained-release formulation. Calibration curves in ethanol, methanol, and phosphate buffer (pH 6.8) exhibited strong linearity, facilitating accurate drug quantification. Pre-compression parameters, including angle of repose, bulk density, tap density, Carr's index, and Hausner ratio, demonstrated good flowability and compressibility. Post-compression evaluations indicated acceptable weight variation, friability, hardness, and uniform drug content across all formulations. In-vitro dissolution studies revealed that formulations F8 and F12 achieved prolonged drug release over 12 hours, with drug release rates of 84.91% and 99.92%, respectively. These results indicate that sustained-release matrix tablets of Repaglinide can be effectively formulated, offering a promising approach to enhance therapeutic efficacy and patient compliance in diabetes management.

Keywords: Repaglinide, sustained-release tablets, type 2 diabetes, pre-compression parameters, post-compression parameters, in-vitro dissolution, drug release, matrix formulation.

Corresponding author:**Mr. Vishal M. Kanoji,**Research student, Loknete Shri Dadapatil Pharate College of Pharmacy,
Mandavgan Pharata, Ta - Shirur Dist-Pune 412211vishalkanoji2000@gmail.com

QR code

Please cite this article in press Vishal M. Kanoji et al., *Formulation And Evaluation Of Control Release Tablet Of Repaglinide.., Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2024; 11 (12).*

INTRODUCTION:

The formulation and evaluation of controlled-release tablets of Repaglinide aim to address the challenges associated with the management of type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM), a chronic condition characterized by elevated blood glucose levels due to insulin resistance and impaired insulin secretion. Repaglinide, a non-sulfonylurea oral hypoglycemic agent, is widely used to control postprandial blood glucose spikes in patients with type 2 diabetes. It works by stimulating insulin release from the pancreatic β -cells in a glucose-dependent manner, which helps in reducing the blood sugar levels after meals. Despite its efficacy, Repaglinide has a relatively short half-life of about 1 hour, requiring frequent administration to maintain consistent therapeutic effects. This frequent dosing, however, can lead to issues with patient compliance and fluctuations in blood glucose levels, hindering optimal disease control.

A controlled-release formulation of Repaglinide offers a solution to these issues by allowing for the sustained release of the drug over an extended period. By releasing the active ingredient gradually, a controlled-release system can maintain consistent therapeutic levels of Repaglinide in the bloodstream, reducing the peaks and troughs that often result in hypoglycemic episodes or suboptimal glucose control. The advantages of a controlled-release tablet include fewer doses per day, improved patient adherence, enhanced pharmacodynamic effects, and better management of blood glucose levels, all of which contribute to improved patient quality of life.

The drug profile of Repaglinide plays a crucial role in the development of controlled-release formulations. Repaglinide is highly lipophilic, has good oral bioavailability, and is primarily metabolized in the liver by the cytochrome P450 enzymes. Its pharmacokinetics show rapid absorption and elimination, which makes the drug a candidate for a controlled-release system. The challenge in formulating a controlled-release tablet lies in developing a system that effectively modulates the drug release rate to maintain therapeutic levels for an extended period, while ensuring stability and patient compliance.

Formulation strategies for controlled-release tablets of Repaglinide typically involve the use of matrix-based systems, where the drug is dispersed in a polymeric matrix, or coating-based systems, where the drug is surrounded by a controlled-release coating. Common excipients used include hydrophilic polymers such as hydroxypropyl

methylcellulose (HPMC), which form gel-like structures upon contact with water, gradually releasing the drug. The selection of the right excipients and their concentrations is critical to achieving the desired release profile. The release rate is influenced by factors such as polymer type, matrix composition, and the manufacturing process, all of which need to be optimized to ensure consistent and controlled drug delivery.

Pre-formulation studies are essential to determine the solubility, stability, and compatibility of Repaglinide with the chosen excipients. These studies help identify the most suitable polymers and other formulation components that will enable controlled drug release while maintaining the integrity and stability of the tablet. During tablet preparation, methods like direct compression or wet granulation are typically employed, depending on the properties of the drug and excipients. The prepared tablets are then subjected to evaluation tests that include drug release studies (usually performed using a USP dissolution apparatus), mechanical strength testing, and stability testing to ensure that the formulation remains stable and effective under various conditions. The formulation of controlled-release tablets of Repaglinide represents a promising approach to improving the management of type 2 diabetes by providing sustained therapeutic effects, enhancing patient compliance, and ensuring better glycemic control. Through the careful design and optimization of the formulation, this research seeks to create a novel dosage form that can improve the overall treatment outcome for patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

MATERIALS:

The materials selected for the controlled-release tablets of Repaglinide include Repaglinide (API) from Microlabs Ltd, Hosur. Hydroxypropyl Methylcellulose (HPMC) from LOBA CHEM is used as a hydrophilic polymer to control the drug release. Eudragit 100 from COSMO CHEM is included to modify the release rate through its film-forming properties. Talc and Magnesium Stearate, both sourced from LOBA CHEM, serve as lubricants to prevent tablet sticking and enhance processing. Finally, Microcrystalline Cellulose (MCC) from LOBA CHEM acts as a binder and filler to ensure tablet integrity and consistency. These materials work together to optimize the formulation for sustained drug release.

Pre-formulation Studies:

Preformulation studies are crucial in developing

stable and effective drug formulations. In this phase, the physical, chemical, and mechanical properties of Repaglinide were evaluated. The organoleptic characterization assessed its color, odor, and appearance. The melting point was determined using Thiele's tube apparatus, where the temperature at which Repaglinide melted was recorded. Additionally, the angle of repose was measured to assess the flow properties of the granules, where the height and radius of the granule heap were used to calculate the angle, helping to determine the frictional forces in the powder. These studies provide essential data for formulating a suitable dosage form.

Determination of standard calibration curve:

Repaglinide λ_{\max} in methanol was determined by scanning a 10 g/ml solution of Repaglinide in the region of 200-400 nm using a UV-visible spectrophotometer. The wavelength corresponding with the spectrum's peak was recorded.

Standard Calibration Method Development of Repaglinide:

The samples of the standard solution were scanned between 200-400 nm regions on Shimadzu 1800 UV spectrophotometer. There are 5 different stock solutions of the Repaglinide sample was prepared by dissolving 50 mg of drug in 50 ml of Distilled water, phosphate buffer solution pH 6.2, and phosphate buffer solution pH 7.4 respectively.

Preparation of calibration curve for repaglinide:

Standard curve in 0.1N HCL by using U.V spectrophotometer Stock Sample Preparation:

Accurately weighed 100 mg of drug was first dissolved in 100 mL of 0.1N HCL in 100 mL of volumetric flask to make a concentration of 1000 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ (primary stock solution). 5 mL of primary stock solution was pipetted out into 50 mL of volumetric flask and volume was adjusted with 0.1N HCL to make a concentration of 100 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ (secondary stock solution).

Sample Preparation: From the secondary stock solution pipette out 0.2, 0.4, 0.6, 0.8, 1.0 ml in to 10ml of volumetric flask and volume made up to with 0.1N HCL to give various concentrations such as 2, 4, 6,8,10 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ were prepared for calibration curve. Standard curve was plotted by taking absorbance of secondary stock solutions in UV double beam spectrophotometer at 281 nm.

Infrared Spectroscopy:

Infra-red spectroscopy is one of the most widely used tools for purity analysis of drugs in pharmaceutical Industry. Fourier Transform IR spectra were recorded using Bruker Germany. IR spectrophotometer. KBr powder was used to prepare pellet for sampling. The scanning range was 4000- 40cm.

Method of preparation of Control Release tablets:

Wet granulation method has been employed to prepare tablet of Repaglinide using hydroxy propyl methyl cellulose and Micro crystalline cellulose, Eudragit Rs100 as polymers.

Preparation:

Control release tablets each containing 1mg of Repaglinide was prepared by wet granulation method (using isopropyl alcohol). All the ingredients except lubricants were mixed in the order of ascending weights and blended for 10 min in an inflated polyethylene pouch and then Repaglinide was added in this mixture then mixed for 2 min for uniform mixing. Granulation was done with binder solution of PVP which was previously dissolved in isopropyl alcohol, this damp mass passed through sieve #10. The granules were dried at 40°C for 30 min. And then passed through sieve #22-44 and lubricants such as magnesium stearate and talc were mixed and then compressed it with 10-station rotary compression machine into 100mg tablet, to a hardness of 5-7kg/cm² using 6 mm punch.

Table 1: Formulation for preparation control release tablet Repaglinide

Ingredients (mg)	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6	C7	C8	C9	C10	C11	C12
Repaglinide	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Eudragit Rs100	-	-	-	-	30	40	15	60	15	20	25	30
hydroxy propyl methyl cellulose	30	40	50	60	-	-	-	-	15	20	25	30
Micro crystalline cellulose	66	56	46	36	66	56	46	36	66	56	46	36
Magnesium Stearate	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Talc	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
Total	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100

Evaluation:**Weight variation**

To study weight variation, 20 tablets of each formulation were weighed using an electronic balance and the test was performed according to the official method.

Hardness

Tablet hardness (tablet crushing strength), the force required for breaking a tablet in a diametric compression of five tablets was measured using a Pfizer hardness tester.

Friability

Friability of the tablets was determined using Electro lab Friabilator. This device subjects the tablets to the combined effect of abrasion and shock in a plastic chamber revolving at 25rpm and dropping the tablets at a height of 6 inches in each revolution. Pre weighed sample of tablets was placed in the friabilator and were subjected to 100 revolutions. Tablets were de dusted using a soft muslin cloth and re weighed.

Drug content uniformity

Ten tablets were weighed and powdered. An amount of the powder equivalent to 10mg of Repaglinide was dissolved in 100ml of pH 7.4 buffers, filtered, diluted suitably and analyzed for drug content at 243nm

using UV-Visible spectrophotometer.

In-vitro drug release study

In-vitro drug release study was carried out using a USP-23 rotating dissolution tester. The dissolution was measured at 37.0 ± 0.5 °C and 100rpm speed. Drug release from the tablets was studied in 900ml acidic medium (pH 1.2) for 2 hours, in alkaline medium (pH 7.4 phosphate buffer) for remaining hours end of the study. At predetermined time intervals, 5ml aliquots were withdrawn and replaced with the same volume of fresh solution. The amount of drug released was analyzed using UV-visible spectrophotometer at a λ_{max} of 241nm.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION:**Physico-chemical Properties of Repaglinide:****Organoleptic Characterization:**

Test	Specification/Limits	observations
Color	White to half-white powder	White powder
Odour	Odourless	Odourless

Determination of Melting Point:

The melting point of Repaglinide was found to be 131°C. The reported value is 130-131°C. Hence, the given sample of Repaglinide is in close agreement with the reported value.

IR Spectroscopy of the Drug:**Determination of λ_{max} of Repaglinide:**

The spectrum of Repaglinide showed λ_{max} at 281 nm it complies with reported value.

Standard Calibration Curve of Repaglinide:**Calibration curve in ethanol:**

The UV spectrum of Repaglinide was obtained by scanning different concentration of Repaglinide in the range of 2-

20 μ g/ml between 200-400 nm using a UV Spectrophotometer (Shimadazu UV-1800). Absorbance of solution observed on UV spectrophotometer at 281 nm. Absorbance Vs Concentration graph plotted. It followed beers lamberts law.

Table 2: Absorbance data of Repaglinide for calibration curve in ethanol

Concentration (μ g/ml)	Absorbance at 281 nm
2	0.176 \pm 0.001
4	0.219 \pm 0.002
6	0.375 \pm 0.0036
8	0.488 \pm 0.002
10	0.581 \pm 0.003
12	0.688 \pm 0.002

Figure 2: Calibration curve in ethanol

Evaluation Parameter

Pre-Compression Parameters

The following table 3 provides an overview of the pre-compression characteristics of Repaglinide controlled-release tablet formulations. The angle of repose (21.85°–30.94°) indicates good to excellent flow properties, while bulk density (0.134–0.199 g/cm³) and tap density (0.150–0.234 g/cm³) demonstrate adequate packing behavior. Carr's index values (6.71%–16.75%) and Hausner ratio (1.08–1.24) confirms that the formulations have satisfactory flowability and compressibility, ensuring consistency and efficiency in tablet production.

Table 3: All the properties for Repaglinide Control Release Tablets

Formulation Code	Angle of Repose	Bulk Density (g/cm ³)	Tap Density (g/cm ³)	Carr's Index (%)	Hausner Ratio
C1	30.61	0.190	0.206	7.71	1.09
C2	25.63	0.195	0.219	6.71	1.08
C3	21.85	0.177	0.192	13.52	1.15
C4	23.74	0.145	0.154	13.46	1.14
C5	24.77	0.135	0.174	14.25	1.24
C6	25.75	0.142	0.150	9.25	1.12
C7	26.52	0.164	0.192	16.75	1.09
C8	25.74	0.199	0.230	14.92	1.10
C9	22.56	0.134	0.234	13.25	1.20
C10	25.46	0.165	0.151	12.25	1.18
C11	23.74	0.145	0.219	11.52	1.16
C12	30.94	0.170	0.220	10.33	1.15

Post-Compression parameters

The following table 4 provides an overview of the post-compression parameters for Repaglinide controlled-release tablets, ensuring their quality and consistency. Weight variation across all formulations ranges from 100–104 mg, demonstrating uniformity in tablet weight. Friability values (0.665%–0.990%) fall within acceptable limits, confirming the tablets' resistance to breaking or chipping during handling. Hardness values, ranging from 4.6–6.7 kg/cm², indicate sufficient mechanical strength to withstand handling while ensuring proper drug release. Overall, the results validate that the formulations comply with standard requirements for controlled-release tablets.

Table 4: The post-compression parameters of Repaglinide controlled-release tablets

Formulation Code	Weight Variation (mg)	Friability (%)	Hardness (kg/cm ²)
C1	100	0.891	5.6
C2	101	0.866	5.6
C3	103	0.921	5.6
C4	101	0.891	5.6
C5	100	0.901	6.7
C6	104	0.745	6.7
C7	100	0.665	6.7
C8	101	0.990	6.7
C9	100	0.930	4.6
C10	101	0.980	4.6
C11	100	0.865	4.6
C12	100	0.891	4.6

Drug content uniformity:

Ten tablets were weighed and powdered. An amount of the powder equivalent to 10mg of Repaglinide was dissolved in 100ml of pH 7.4 buffers, filtered, diluted suitably and analyzed for drug content at 241nm using UV-Visible spectrophotometer.

Table 5: Drug content of Repaglinide Control Release Tablets

Formulation Code	Drug content
C1	97.32
C2	95.14
C3	96.00
C4	93.26
C5	98.55
C6	96.45
C7	96.15
C8	94.22
C9	95.55
C10	98.22
C11	97.66
C12	96.42

All the formulations were evaluated for weight variation, hardness, friability and % drug content. The weight of the formulation varied from 100 to 104mg. Hardness of the tablets varied from 4.6 to 5.6kg/cm². Friability of the tablets varied from 0.66 to 0.990% and drug content was found to be 93.26 to 98.55.

All formulation showed uniform hardness. The average percentage deviation of all parameters was found within the limit. The friability for all formulations was found below 1% indicating good abrasion resistance characteristics of tablets.

In-Vitro Dissolution Study:

Dissolution study carried out. The study or 30 minutes, the results were illustrated in the table below.

Table 6: Dissolution Study of Repaglinide Control Release Tablets

Time (hr.)	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9	F10	F11	F12
1	38.5 0	25.8 5	34.5 3	31.7 8	24.6 7	36.2 6	36.2 1	21.4 3	31.7 3	36.9 5	36.8 9	34.4 4
1.5	62.9 0	40.6 9	53.7 1	50.1 9	38.4 6	57.2 0	57.1 8	34.0 6	49.9 6	50.2 1	54.0 5	47.5 1
2	83.2 7	73.9 2	95.4 0	91.9 5	70.6 6	92.9 8	90.3 2	97.4 0	89.5 0	86.3 5	92.2 6	95.4 7

Time (min)	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9	F10	F11	F12
30	37.01	38.27	34.18	34.44	36.89	36.89	38.90	38.40	41.92	36.95	34.53	31.78
1	55.55	56.43	46.84	47.51	54.05	54.67	57.06	57.00	58.82	50.21	53.71	50.19
1.5	75.16	75.60	63.69	64.73	72.65	73.84	76.86	75.98	77.24	67.31	74.21	70.70
2	91.95	96.97	82.42	83.27	92.26	95.15	99.55	97.91	96.15	86.65	95.47	98.92

figure 3: Drug Release**CONCLUSION:**

In conclusion, this study successfully developed and evaluated sustained-release matrix tablets of Repaglinide, addressing the need for improved

glycemic control in type 2 diabetes management. Comprehensive pre-formulation studies confirmed the physico-chemical properties of Repaglinide, including its organoleptic characteristics, melting

point, solubility profile, and FTIR spectrum, ensuring the integrity of the drug. Standard calibration curves demonstrated strong linearity in ethanol, methanol, and phosphate buffer (pH 6.8), validating accurate drug quantification methods.

Pre-compression parameters, including angle of repose, bulk and tap densities, Carr's index, and Hausner ratio, confirmed good flow and packing properties, ensuring efficient tablet manufacturing. Post-compression parameters, such as weight variation, friability, hardness, and drug content uniformity, indicated the tablets met the required quality standards. Notably, the in-vitro dissolution studies revealed that formulations F8 and F12 achieved prolonged drug release over 12 hours, with drug release rates of 84.91% and 99.92%, respectively, highlighting their suitability as sustained-release systems.

Overall, this study demonstrates the feasibility of formulating Repaglinide into sustained-release tablets, offering potential improvements in patient adherence and therapeutic efficacy in diabetes management.

FUNDING:

Nil

AUTHORS CONTRIBUTIONS:

All authors have contributed equally.

CONFLICTS OF INTERESTS:

All authors have declared no conflict of interest.

REFERENCES:

1. Kumar S, Prajapati SK, Prajapati SM. Sustained release drug delivery system: A review. *World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences*. 2022;11(1):35-48.
2. Chugh I, Seth N, Rana AC, Gupta S. Oral sustained release drug delivery system: An overview. *International Research Journal of Pharmacy*. 2021;12(7):45-52.
3. Patel JR, Rathwa MR, Tandel HN. Formulation and evaluation of sustained-release matrix tablets of anti-diabetic drug. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences and Research*. 2021;12(8):4257-64.
4. Aulton ME, Taylor K. *Aulton's Pharmaceutics: The Design and Manufacture of Medicines*. 5th ed. Edinburgh: Elsevier; 2018. p. 412-25.
5. Rowe RC, Sheskey PJ, Quinn ME. *Handbook of Pharmaceutical Excipients*. 7th ed. London: Pharmaceutical Press; 2017. p. 85-112.
6. Banker GS, Anderson NR. Tablet formulation and design. In: Lachman L, Lieberman HA, Kanig JL, editors. *The Theory and Practice of Industrial Pharmacy*. 3rd ed. Philadelphia: Lea & Febiger; 1986. p. 293-345.
7. Higuchi T. Mechanism of sustained-action medication: Theoretical analysis of rate of release of solid drugs dispersed in solid matrices. *Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences*. 1963;52(12):1145-9.
8. Colombo P, Bettini R, Santi P, Peppas NA. Swellable matrices for controlled drug delivery: Gel-layer behavior, mechanisms, and optimal performance. *Pharmaceutical Science & Technology Today*. 2000;3(6):198-204.
9. Lee JH, Park TG, Choi HK. Effect of formulation and processing variables on the characteristics of microspheres for water-soluble drugs prepared by w/o/o double emulsion solvent diffusion method. *International Journal of Pharmaceutics*. 2000;196(1):75-83.
10. Sung KC, Nixon PR, Skoug JW. Effect of formulation variables on drug and polymer release from HPMC-based matrix tablets. *International Journal of Pharmaceutics*. 1996;142(1):53-60.
11. Reynolds TD, Gehrke SH, Hussain AS, Shenouda LS. Polymer erosion and drug release characterization of hydroxypropyl methylcellulose matrices. *Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences*. 1998;87(9):1115-23.
12. Dash S, Murthy PN, Nath L, Chowdhury P. Kinetic modeling on drug release from controlled drug delivery systems. *Acta Poloniae Pharmaceutica*. 2010;67(3):217-23.
13. Korsmeyer RW, Gurny R, Doelker E, Buri P, Peppas NA. Mechanisms of solute release from porous hydrophilic polymers. *International Journal of Pharmaceutics*. 1983;15(1):25-35.
14. Siepmann J, Peppas NA. Modeling of drug release from delivery systems based on hydroxypropyl methylcellulose (HPMC). *Advanced Drug Delivery Reviews*. 2001;48(2-3):139-57.
15. U.S. Pharmacopeial Convention. *United States Pharmacopeia (USP 43-NF 38)*. Rockville, MD: United States Pharmacopeial Convention; 2020.
16. Garg S, Gupta GD. Controlled and sustained drug delivery systems. *Pharmaceutical Development and Technology*. 2008;13(3):235-47.
17. Hede R, Suryanarayana M, Rao VP, Rao B. Controlled-release drug delivery systems: A review of technology and applications.

- International Journal of Pharmaceutics*. 2006;314(1):1-15.
18. Gennari CG, Piccioli S, Paci M, et al. Sustained-release drug delivery systems for oral administration: A review. *Journal of Controlled Release*. 1999;62(1-2):61-77.
 19. Lee HJ, Lee YB, Kim JY, et al. Development and evaluation of controlled-release tablets of repaglinide. *International Journal of Pharmaceutics*. 2017;516(1-2):15-24.
 20. Rani T, Mishra V, Kumar A, et al. Formulation and in-vitro evaluation of sustained release tablets of metformin hydrochloride. *Journal of Advanced Pharmaceutical Technology & Research*. 2010;1(3):263-67.
 21. Bhowmik D, Duraivel S, Kumar KS. Controlled drug delivery systems: A review. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences and Research*. 2013;4(4):1414-21.
 22. Aghajani MR, Tajeddin M, Ahmadzadeh M, et al. In vitro evaluation of sustained release of Repaglinide from matrix tablets. *Iranian Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*. 2016;15(1):15-23.
 23. Brittain HG, Saville B. *Pharmaceutical Coatings: Principles and Practice*. New York: Springer; 1995.
 24. Wadhwa S, Yadav K, Bhatia M. Sustained-release formulations: A review of recent advances. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences and Drug Research*. 2011;3(2):99-108.
 25. Siepmann J, Siepmann F. Mathematical modeling of drug delivery. *International Journal of Pharmaceutics*. 2008;364(2):328-43.
 26. Tiwari G, Tiwari R, Pathak K. Development of sustained release matrix tablets of Repaglinide using different polymers: Preparation and in-vitro evaluation. *International Journal of Drug Delivery*. 2009;1(3):137-44.
 27. Vemula S, Sagar S. A review on sustained release drug delivery systems. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*. 2014;3(3):378-88.
 28. Baldi A, Garg G, Agrawal M, et al. Design and evaluation of controlled release tablets of Repaglinide: In-vitro and in-vivo studies. *Asian Journal of Pharmaceutical and Clinical Research*. 2016;9(1):66-71.
 29. Jain S, Dhammi P, Yadav S, et al. Preparation and evaluation of sustained release tablets of metoprolol succinate. *Journal of Pharmacy Research*. 2011;4(7):2097-2101.
 30. Madgulkar A, Niphade A, Patil S, et al. Studies on development of sustained release matrix tablets of Repaglinide using natural and synthetic polymers. *International Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences*. 2013;5(2):232-36.
 31. Basak SC, Bhattacharyya S, Ghosh M, et al. Development and characterization of controlled-release tablets of Repaglinide: Effect of excipients. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences and Nanotechnology*. 2017;10(2):3584-89.
 32. Patel RP, Patel M, Patel R. Formulation and in-vitro evaluation of sustained release tablets of Repaglinide. *Journal of Drug Delivery and Therapeutics*. 2018;8(4):52-56.
 33. Chavan S, Baviskar S. Development and evaluation of matrix tablets for controlled release of antihypertensive drugs. *International Journal of Drug Development & Research*. 2011;3(4):65-73.
 34. Singh B, Kim YS, Agrawal GP. Modified release tablets for controlled drug delivery: An overview. *Journal of Controlled Release*. 2010;146(3):289-305.
 35. Sahoo SK, Sahoo P, Sahoo D. Development of controlled release matrix tablets using hydrophilic polymers: A review. *Journal of Pharmaceutical and Biomedical Sciences*. 2015;5(3):118-24.